

Supplementary data - List of Included studies (Research Design)

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Table 1: Final list of included studies

Title	Reference	Year	Origin
Guidelines for the search strategy to update systematic literature reviews in software engineering	[1]	2020	Seed set
When to update systematic literature reviews in software engineering	[2]	2020	Seed set
Knowledge Management for Promoting Update of Systematic Literature Reviews: An Experience Report	[3]	2020	Seed set
Reducing efforts of software engineering systematic literature reviews updates using text classification	[4]	2020	Seed set
Avoiding plagiarism in systematic literature reviews: An update concern	[5]	2020	Snowballing
On the need to update systematic literature reviews	[6]	2019	Seed set
Evaluating Strategies for Forward Snowballing Application to Support Secondary Studies Updates: Emergent Results	[7]	2018	Seed set
Maintaining Systematic Literature Reviews: Benefits and Drawbacks	[8]	2018	Snowballing
An Experience Report on Update of Systematic Literature Reviews	[9]	2017	Seed set
A Visual Analysis Approach to Update Systematic Reviews	[10]	2014	Snowballing
Guidelines for Snowballing in Systematic Literature Studies and a Replication in Software Engineering	[11]	2014	Snowballing
Using Forward Snowballing to update Systematic Reviews in Software Engineering	[12]	2016	Seed set
Formalizing a Systematic Review Updating Process	[13]	2008	Seed set
Experimenting with a multi-iteration systematic review in software engineering	[14]	2008	Snowballing

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